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Audiovisual narratives of the Sami people at the beginnings of the Eurovision Song Contest (1960–1980)

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ABSTRACT

Held annually since 1956 and attracting the continuing participation of most European countries, the Eurovision Song Contest (ESC) is usually defined as the audiovisual counterpart to the contemporary history of the continent. Regarding this issue, the narratives incorporated into the performances by each state television network can be understood as aesthetic-political messages. This is made explicit primarily by means of the performers' place of origin, the chosen musical style and the language of the song lyrics. In this sense, the case of the Sami ethnic minority, inhabiting four countries—Norway, Sweden, Finland, and Russia—is paradigmatic. Not constituting a *de jure* nation, their participation in the competition is only possible through other, officially recognised nation-states—a situation that has recurred several times in the contest. For this reason, this study will concentrate on the visibility of this community in the ESC. The focus will be put on its first two decades (1960–1980), a crucial time for the assertion of the rights of the Sami people, analysing three entries that set a precedent as to how this ethnic group would be represented in the context of the culture of spectacle, and at the same time suggesting their own particular audiovisual narratives.

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1. Introduction and theoretical framework

The Eurovision Song Contest (ESC) is a music competition organised by the European Broadcasting Union (EBU) in which different state television networks, mainly European, meet annually to *compete* for victory but also to *share* before an international audience (Yair, 2019, pp. 1013–1014) its music, its customs (Panea, 2020, p. 27), and even its values (Fornäs, 2017, p. 182). Although many of those corporations often submit pop songs not referring in any way to their local traditions, inasmuch as the contest requires that every performer represent a state television, aesthetic and political identifications inevitably arise (Fricker, 2015, p. 8; Pajala, 2013, p. 78). Such a unique competition, framed in the field of 'media-events' and 'mega-events' (Bolin, 2010, pp. 125–126), results in a 'total social phenomenon' (Petersen & Ren, 2015, pp. 99–100). Furthermore, its longevity makes the show a pertinent object of study through which to approach European history and the aesthetic tastes prevailing in the continent in the field of popular culture over the last few decades (Arntsen, 2005, p. 154).

The reasons mentioned above point to the importance of the concept of *narrative* in the ESC (Pajala, 2011, p. 408) and, additionally, to the spirit on which it was founded: that on which the project of the future European Union (EU) was also built (Pajala, 2013, p. 81). Thus, the contest is 'a discourse from and on Europe' (Lampropoulos, 2013, p. 140)—as well as *on the West against the East*—that emerged in the middle of the Cold War (Oliver, 2011, 7'15"). When talking about 'discourse', the very ability of narrate is relevant here because it brings to the table the figure of the narrator: the one who has the power to enunciate a message and at the same time be listened to (Martínez-Collado, 2008). This concept is interesting to this investigation in order to find the relationship between the voice of a minority such as the

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Sami and the mainstream context of a media event such as Eurovision, very tied too with European institutions.

Regarding this issue, from the 1940s, some institutions such as the British Council and the United States Information Service were seeking to get closer to the Eastern Bloc by means of 'the musical programmes of Western radio stations, especially the BBC, Radio Free Europe, Radio Luxembourg and The Voice of America' (Vuletic, 2018, p. 93). For that matter, since its inception the ESC had been broadcast over the OIRT network (an analogue to the UER) throughout the satellite countries of the Soviet Union (Fornäs, 2017, p. 185), which proves how the contest was born with the will to reach the largest number of potential audiences—even those situated in the cultural and ideological antipodes of the emerging 'new' European society (Hilder, 2017, p. 29; Yair, 2019, p. 1017). Additionally, other values held by the not-yet ratified European Constitution have been displayed in the contest, especially the recognition of cultural diversity sanctioned through agreements such as the Lisbon Treaty (2007) (Hilder, 2017, p. 28).

With regard to this diversity, even though the homogenising idea of a single *narrative* of Europe has been widely illustrated in the contest by countless stereotyped commercial pop songs, some remarkable and highly significant entries based on the local culture can also be detected (Yair, 2019, p. 1015). These performances have helped make certain minorities visible while motivating shifts in the way the public tend to perceive them (Hilder, 2017, p. 29). This is especially relevant when these minorities do not properly form a state, or their recognition is limited. These entries, however critical of the most widespread and accepted musical styles, were not able by themselves to escape sometimes from falling into certain clichés (p. 33). The very structure of the show, in which each song is allowed to be performed only once and to last no longer than three minutes, forces the messages to be compressed and rendered as accessible as possible (Kalvig, 2020, p. 13; Singleton et al., 2007, p. 17).

Although the more 'ethnic' contributions are in the minority, it is worth highlighting them since they can be postulated as narratives of resistance against the more mainstream entries. An ethnic group, in general terms, is a community whose members perceive themselves as such by carrying out a set of customs, by speaking a common language and, to a lesser extent, by sharing the same territory and certain phenotypic traits (Bhabha, 2011, p. 100; Stolcke, 2011, p. 325). But such a highly problematic concept does not serve to define large population groups, as nations are, which would hardly fit in the definition, in addition to the fact that nations often bring together different ethnic groups (Motschenbacher, 2016, p. 71). Consequently, ethnicity is rather equated with kinship structures, its constitutive elements being so specific that any extrapolation to larger human groups would prove quite complicated (Giménez, 2006, p. 141). If the concept of *resistance* is brought up precisely at this point of the analysis of the ESC it is, therefore, because the above-mentioned entries that tackle ethnic and local issues are inescapably excluded from the mainstream and from reaching wide audiences. They may sound odd, unfamiliar or simply funny, even picturesque, to the general public, failing both in the contest and outside it, as has often been the case (Motschenbacher, 2016, p. 44; Yair, 2019, p. 1017).

As to the concept of narrative, this term can be interpreted as an act of power or domination (Jarque, 2002, pp. 53–54). Narratives involve the desire to create realities, even to impose them, and many of them are socially assumed in our everyday life, accepted uncritically by most human beings. Thus, it might be pertinent to examine the very notion of narration—as postmodernism postulates—to make explicit its agenda, i.e. its politics (Ruiz de Samaniego, 2007, pp. 78–79), in order to be used in a non-imperative, thus reflexive, way. But it is also true that narrating is inherent to the eminently linguistic nature of human beings. Narrating is key to our cognitive structure as far as it facilitates our symbolising ability by the articulation of sentences that, in turn, result in texts and messages, thereby guiding our capacity to 'build, inhabit, think', in Martin Heidegger's famous terms (Sánchez Meca, 2005, p. 45).

The type of narration prevailing in the ESC is of an audiovisual nature (Fornäs, 2017, p. 184), and the audiovisual is key to understand our current societies. While it is true that we live among stories, we also live among images, i.e. those '*symbolic forms of knowledge and identity* that are forged among different human cultures to structure spaces of meaning, and that circulate through different expressive means or *languages*' (Jiménez, 2020, p. 15). In fact, the creation of images is a 'specifically human activity', even more specific than speech, as Ana García Varas points out (2011, pp. 35–36). We are always surrounded by images, even more so in our current culture, where they constitute 'the playing ground on which we deliberately move around' (Sánchez Fernández, 2019, p. 13). Indeed, 'getting

completely out of the image is impossible, since that is the social articulation network that structures our world', claims José Jiménez (2020, p. 12). Nonetheless, he adds that 'it is possible [...] to go beyond' the image, which then would enable us, 'through such questioning, to decipher what [it] conceals' (p. 12).

Following this idea, it can be observed that the ESC, as part of the cultural industries, viz. entertainment, has promoted the conveyance of images of quite diverse nature throughout its history—which is no surprise when one considers the number of countries that have participated from 1956 to date. With such a long history, almost entirely available on the internet, the amount of material 'to go beyond' is really extensive (Pajala, 2022, p. 198). In fact, given that some of the TV networks, e.g. the German, Swiss and French ones, have participated in the contest from its inception, it is even possible to pin down different directions or trends from among the songs presented (Hindrichs, 2007, p. 55). Others, such as those of San Marino or Azerbaijan, have just begun to forge their narratives in recent times (Vuletic, 2018, p. 195). Therefore, an analysis of the typology of narratives that each one has outlined should be carried out to understand the multiple dimensions of the show.

As García Varas writes about the role of images in the field of Aesthetics today, a very characteristic feature of our times is the displacement of 'horizontal borders between cultures', which become diffuse and even disappear: 'the Western canon, not only the artistic one but also the visual one in its full extent [...], is seen as *placed at an equal level* with others. In many cases, the *other* cultures have not ceased to be *other*, and fusions and hybrids of different traditions are common' (2011, p. 53). Something similar can be noticed in the evolution of the ESC. Throughout its history, more and more countries have joined in and have then found themselves located quite near each other, despite being opposite in other fields (e.g. in politics) (Fornäs, 2017, p. 189). Though apparently fostering a sort of inclusion awareness, this also sets a divide between the participating states. The images of *ones* and *others* gradually deposit a sediment. They are conveyed 'as crystallisations of life experience [...], hence their durability, the impression of eternity they make on us' (Jiménez, 2020, p. 24).

Images are inherently projective, which is reinforced by our aim and desire to share them. In the case of the ESC, the tendency among the diverse participating nations to follow a single direction, consolidated through aesthetic resources (Fornäs, 2017, p. 184), motivates peculiar habits and methods that shape what each state TV network wants to signify. This is achieved not only by means of the music score, but also through the scenery, the singers' outfits, their performance and the choreography (Pajala, 2022, p. 194). The vocation for projection is also political inasmuch as it often entails the purpose to convey a message—to tell a story (Singleton et al., 2013, p. 101). Therefore, the ESC, watched by many millions of viewers, seems the ideal platform to assert those messages or stories that do not take a prominent position in the headlines of the global map (Yair, 2019, p. 1016).

In this paper, an analysis will be conducted of the most relevant entries in relation to the subjects of their narratives, stressing their potential resistances and establishing links between aesthetics and politics in the case of the Sami contributions to the ESC representing Norway and Finland. In both countries, a great deal of debate has traditionally arisen concerning both European identity (Vuletic, 2018, p. 12) and Sami identity, the latter being part of the national fabric (Berg, 2008, p. 10). Here it can be found, again, the relationship between the local and the global in the contest. In view of the fact that the participation in the ESC can contribute to the promotion of certain national identifications, the show has also become the privileged arena for all the 'marginalized groups' who get together 'to celebrate' its differences 'through music and spectacle' (Waysdorf, 2020, p. 298). Such is the case with its huge popularity among the LGBTIQ+ audience, but also with other subordinate identities (Baker, 2017, p. 110; Hilder, 2017, p. 37). For this reason, it may prove revealing to turn to the case of Sami visibility, in order to create a counterpoint and to challenge the stereotypes and the ideal of national identity as a political fiction (Arntsen, 2005, p. 149, 152).

Finally, regarding the above-mentioned audiovisual nature of the contest, the focus of our investigation will be both the music and the lyrics of the songs selected and the *mise-en-scène* of their performances. The *mise-en-scène* theory (Gibbs, 2002; Martin, 2014; Pavis, 2013) is very useful here to understand the multimedia dimension of the ESC entries beyond the music. Following the description of Sunhee Lee, the *mise-en-scène* encompasses the performer 'position and gestures, costume, set design, props, lighting and audio effects' (2016, p. 412).

2. Objectives and methodology

The main objective of this article is to identify the ways in which the Sami ethnic group was represented in the beginnings of the Eurovision Song Contest. Given that this people have never established itself as a nation-state in its own right, they have needed to take part in the competition through the TV networks of the countries they inhabit, all of them regular contestants. Three cases will be analysed that correspond with three quite different moments between the '60s and the '80s of the last century. The first is the Norwegian entry of 1960, with Nora Brockstedt performing the song 'Voi-Voi', composed by Georg Elgaaen; the second, the 1977 Finnish TV submission, 'Lapponia', sung by Monica Aspelund and authored by Aarno Raninen and herself; and finally, the Norwegian 'Sámiid Ædnan', a song written by Sverre Kjelsberg and Ragnar Olsen and performed by the duo formed by Kjelsberg and Mattis Hætta, who competed in the 1980 edition. A secondary objective is to find the interconnections between all three acts in order to elucidate possible differences in: (a) the motifs present in the representation of the Sami; (b) the costumes, which raises the problem of their staging; and (c) its reception within and without the contest.

An assessment will be carried out as to whether the forging of all these elements has succeeded in making them possible audiovisual narratives of resistance—somehow helping the Sami culture to express itself and to have its image enhanced—or, on the contrary, they have further aestheticised it. Summarising the concept of 'audiovisual narrative' pointed out in the second paragraph of the introduction on the basis of various authors, from Aesthetics (Fricker, 2015; Jarque, 2002; Jiménez, 2020; García Varas, 2011; Ruiz de Samaniego, 2007), Anthropology and Cultural Studies (Baker, 2017; Bhabha, 2003; Björnberg & Bossius, 2017; Lampropoulos, 2013; Yair, 2019) or History of Media (Bolin, 2010; Fornäs, 2017; Pajala, 2011; Vuletic, 2018; Waysdorf, 2020), this concept covers those symbolic practices that use the moving image to send messages that often cannot be expressed textually. Specifically, messages that have to do with the visibilisation of certain stories, often from the everyday, subaltern or underground stories veiled by the hegemony of the mass media. Regarding that point, the term aestheticization is understood here as the process by which symbolic practices—among them, the moving image—whiten and embellish certain problematic or subversive questions by means of evocative and persuasive tools. Its objective, thus, is to deactivate them politically. This question, already studied by authors such as Benjamin (2015, p. 26), resonates strongly today around practices of whitewashing or pinkwashing (Gross, 2015), recently perceivable at the ESC (Baker, 2017, p. 102).

The methodology of this article will be one focused on the case study (Ríos Hernández & Pinto Arboleda, 2019, p. 38), with a primarily exploratory and descriptive approach (Martínez Carazo, 2006), and drawing from the analysis of both audiovisual (viz. the recordings of the ESC) and textual academic sources (i.e. works, both on the contest and on the history of the Sami community, belonging to the fields of Aesthetics, Cultural Studies and Anthropology). The three case studies, the three performances mentioned above have been selected because only they contain references to Sami culture in their songs (lyrics and music) as well as in their *mise-en-scène* in the first twenty years of the competition. Studying these contributions is also inseparable from an investigation of their performers. To find these three examples, all editions of the show during this period have been watched, noting that only three performances address this topic. Nonetheless, although they do not come from the Sami ethnic group, there are more artists born in Lapland who represent—in this case—Norway in the competition during this period. Since they do not include ethnic elements in said proposals, they have simply been mentioned.

However, since 2000 more examples of Sami artists at the ESC can be found—Roger Pontare (Sweden 2000), Agnete (Norway 2016) or Fred Buljo (Norway 2019)—, as well as themes related to their culture, also in the national pre-selections, such as the Swedish Melodifestivalen or the Norwegian Melodi Grand Prix. For this reason, and noting there is hardly any research about these early performances, this study can provide a basis, a solid ground to understand these later entries in future research. The investigation will be accompanied by a parallel analysis of the Sami resistance movements in these decades, drawing on the most relevant literature on the subject (among others, see Gaski, 2008; Hilder, 2015; Jones-Bamman, 2001; Kalvig, 2020; Paine, 1985; Ren & Thisted, 2021; Svensson, 1987). The aim is thus to examine in greater depth the context in which these three entries were born, also targeting other related Sami

artists in this time, even if they are not properly involved in the competition. All in all, a broader perspective on the three entries studied will be attained, which will afford a better understanding of them, in line with some of the latest methodologies (focused indeed on the contest itself), like the propounded by Gómez-Pérez and Pérez-Rufí (2022) and Pérez-Rufí and Valverde-Maestre (2020).

3. The Sami people and the ESC

The Sami people, commonly labeled as ‘the only indigenous people in the European Union’ (Ren & Thisted, 2021, p. 302), inhabits a region in northern Scandinavia internationally known as Lapland, which they call ‘Sápmi’ (Hansen, 2015, p. 3). The term ‘indigenous’ having replaced the former ‘primitive’ (Ren & Thisted 2021, p. 303), it still designates those communities that maintain a sound oral and spiritual tradition, as opposed to ‘modern’ societies, and lack ‘complex administrative structures’ (p. 303). In this regard, Dyck (1985) and Alfred (1999), among others, provided a thorough understanding of indigenous identity in the context of the emergence of Cultural Studies, and which relationship with nationalism (Hobsbawm & Ranger, 2000) has been recently studied too (Oksanen, 2020). At that point, it is noteworthy to state that the nationalism expressed by indigenous people is based not so much in a question of borders, but in the preservation of cultural practices or ways of life, where aesthetics plays a key role.

According to Oksanen ‘indigenous nationalism is not premised on establishing new nation-states, or on capturing existing ones, but on renegotiating indigenous–settler-state relations to gain acceptance for indigenous customary practices as the basis for self-governance’ (2020, p. 1154). In the concrete case of the Sami people, despite the fact that the United Nations report *Our Common Future* (1987) upholds the idea that these people possess a vast treasure of ‘experiential’ wealth (Ren & Thisted 2021, p. 303), they have constantly suffered the consequences of imperialism throughout history (Hilder, 2017, p. 29). This is a shared story with other indigenous around the globe, as in the case of Australian Aboriginals, a topic also studied in the context of the ESC due to the recent participation of Australia’s TV broadcaster SBS (Collins & Barker, 2019).

Having lived in isolation for centuries due to the lack of appeal of their inhospitable land, the northwards expansion of the kingdoms of Sweden and Norway in the 16th century (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 199) would end up colliding with the Sami territory, which then became restricted to a west-east strip along the north coast of Scandinavia (Ren & Thisted 2021, p. 303). As early as in 1595 and 1613, the treaties of Tåyssinä and Knäred entailed the first partition of Lapland between Sweden and Norway. In 1751, the Lapp Codicil was signed, allowing the Sami to herd their reindeer freely and to maintain their traditional ways of life (Berg, 2008, p. 10). However, the expansion of railways and highways in the 19th and 20th centuries once again cut off the deer migration routes and their grazing areas (Ahlness & Gauto, 2019, p. 64).

With the rise of nationalisms, a series of assimilation policies spread, including the Sami being violently forced to convert to Christianity (Ahlness & Gauto, 2019, p. 64). Their language was also prohibited. The constant discrimination they suffered (Berg, 2008, p. 11) exploded in the Kautokeino Revolution (1858), when ‘a group of Sami rose up against the Norwegian authorities and exploitative merchants’ (Ahlness & Gauto, 2019, p. 65). But only in the 20th century would ‘the first pan-Sámi meeting’ take place, ‘in Trondheim in 1917’ (Hilder, 2015, p. 35). However, after Finland had aligned itself with the Nazi Germany, the Lapland War (1944–1945) led to the devastation of their towns by the Red Army. Only after the passing of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights by the UN in 1948 could the Sami effectively assert their rights, making a significant breakthrough in this regard (Berg, 2008, p. 11). From the 1950s onwards they started an aesthetic-political movement (involving music among other cultural expressions), which, in the absence of sound institutions, became an alternative tool for recognition. It was at that point when the ESC was born.

Although being a national of the country is not an ESC prerequisite for either the composers or the performers of a participant in the competition, as far as the Sami represent a part of their territory there are four countries that would more likely be willing to incorporate them into their respective competing delegations. They are Norway (which participates through the state TV network NRK), Sweden (through the SVT), Finland (through the YLE), and Russia (through the C1R).¹ Thus, ‘under the national confines of the ESC, the indigenous or other sub-national identities can only enter under the auspices of states

(through their broadcasting companies)' (Ren & Thisted 2021, p. 311). However, these communities can take the opportunity to subvert, in their own best interest, the very framework they are afforded (p. 311). Whereas Russia (when still a member of the EBU) never made the Sami problem visible, the Norwegian, Swedish and Finnish TV networks have done so, in diverse ways.

On account of the persistence of the identity-driven calls to the concept of nation, not only through music, but also through images hoisting that concept (Billig, 2014, p. 24), it is inevitable to read the audiovisual productions performed in the ESC in political terms, as mentioned above (Fornäs, 2017, p. 189; Lampropoulos, 2013, p. 141). In fact, the staging has, since the first edition, stood out for the incorporation of visual elements that accompany the narratives of the participating songs, with an increasing 'emphasis on the spectacle' (Pajala, 2011, p. 410)—noticeable in the sophistication of the costumes and the introduction of choreography and props, arranged by the competing delegations to dialogue with the hosting stage (Pajala, 2022, p. 193).

Overall, a great variety of set designs are found throughout the history of the ESC. Some projects simply show off the possibilities of the space, lighting and TV production, adding spectacular props too. Others prefer to address some thematic lines, so often related to the culture of the host country, inspired by its cities, its cultural heritage or its landscapes (Panea, 2020, p. 34; 2022, p. 233). However, as stage elements at large were still rare in the ESC in the period covered by this study, the set design is not really a significant feature. Similarly, other visual elements, such as the 'postcards' (the short introductory videos aired between the performances) and the promotional music videos of the contestants, only later became established. Nonetheless, an exception will be mentioned below—'Lapponia'—which rare music video will be relevant for the analysis. In sum, the most important visual elements on those entries are related to outfits, and in a minor way lighting and live production.

3.1. 'Voi-voi' (1960) and the Sami during the 1950s and 1960s

Given that the Sami do not constitute an independent nation-state, with their population spread across several countries, it initially seemed unlikely that they would manage to be represented in any way at the ESC. However, it was the song with which Norway made its debut in the contest—in the London 1960 edition—the one that first directly alluded to this community (Hilder, 2017, p. 32). On that occasion, the NRK signed the performer Nora Brockstedt (Oslo, 1923–2015), who sang Georg Elgaaen's song 'Voi-voi'. Even though this title includes an expression in the Sami language, this was in fact the only nod to the vernacular. The remainder of the lyrics were fully written in Norwegian.

'Voi-voi' appeared in a context of heated debate on the Sami question. Only four years before, in 1956, the Nordic Sami Council was founded (Berg, 2008, p. 11) and a Sami committee proposed to break away from the 'Norwegianisation' policy, a petition passed in the Norwegian Parliament in 1960 (p. 11). Nonetheless, music was, as mentioned above, an alternative way to spread their messages, at that time beginning to have an impact on the Scandinavian countries (Hilder, 2015, pp. 58–59). The best-known performer from that decade was Sven-Gösta Jonsson, who sang in Swedish (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 192) and would incorporate jazz and rock sounds into his songs, as Elgaaen did. The main purpose of these creations was to spread Sami culture, through lyrics, normally in Swedish, Norwegian, or Finnish (p. 195). In fact, at the time under focus most of the singers could barely speak the Sami languages, which comes as no surprise when considering the assimilation policies prevailed for more than two centuries (p. 191). Likewise, the *joik*, a traditional singing technique, was only occasionally mentioned in the lyrics of Elgaaen's song (pp. 192–193).

From a musical and lyrical perspective, 'Voi-voi' mirrors Jonsson's works. It is an *up-tempo* song, in which 'the minor-mode song is accompanied by full orchestra and jazz band' (Hilder, 2017, p. 33). Its short duration (2'30") and intricate structure (chorus – two stanzas – chorus – instrumental bridge – chorus) make it a truly dynamic piece, with 'the playful orchestral writing' (Hilder, 2015, p. 58) standing out. While the music has nothing to do with the Sami culture, the lyrics describe a relationship between a Sami girl and her boyfriend. She comes apparently from the south of the country, from an indeterminate region referred to as 'the valley'. 'Voi-voi, voi-voi, high up there in the mountains, can you hear my greeting?', sings the girl repeatedly (Brockstedt, 1960). The utterance of the peculiar greeting is thus highlighted by the subsequent question about it.

Another remarkable excerpt goes as follows: ‘*Voi-voi*, I want to tell you I’m waiting for you. In a small valley, far to the north, where the sun shines all night long. In a small valley, far to the north, I heard a Sami girl sing’ (Brockstedt, 1960). While the song is obviously about the wait and the fate of the girl (both common tropes in light music to address feminine condition), at the same time suggests the possibility for her to go down to the valley, ‘on Saturday night’, to see her sweetheart. Despite the emphasis on ‘heteronormative desire’ and ‘classic gender roles’ (Hilder, 2017, pp. 33–34), the lyrics can also be construed as dealing with the relations between two distant bodies, two distant cultures too (Fornäs, 2017, p. 214). The possibility of their rapprochement is hinted at, although through the dichotomy between masculine and feminine, all of it in the shape of a call to romantic love livening up the act.

On a visual level, the entry is reminiscent of Sami aesthetics through the *gákti* dress she wore (Kalvig, 2020, p. 7), albeit in a white version—also featured on the cover of the single—of the colourful original. On account of this detail, the proposal ‘is often criticised today for its exoticised representation of the Sámi’ (Hilder, 2015, p. 58). Actually, Brockstedt is not of Sami descent nor was anyone in the production team (p. 58). Especially interesting is the cover of the vinyl containing the piece, which shows the singer in a forest in the role of the girl the song is about, next to a speech bubble including the expression ‘*Voi-voi*’. All these visual elements reinforce the exoticism of the content, framed in a rural setting. As regards the scenery, the production presented by the BBC (which organised the event that year) was a remarkable display (Pajala, 2022, p. 192). In order to explicitly allude to the setting depicted by the song, a background set consisting of a board cut-out in triangular shapes resembling a mountainous landscape was built for Brockstedt’s performance. Regarding to the TV production, only four shots compound this audiovisual piece: two American shots of the singer taken frontally, a full shot of the seated public in the theatre, and a medium shot taken obliquely, which establishes a greater closeness between spectator and singer.

Despite the clichés, such was the reception of the song that the singer returned to the competition the following year (O’Connor, 2007, p. 19) with the song ‘*Sommer i Palma*’, composed by Jan Wølner and Egil Hagen (Brockstedt, 1961), but in this case not related to Sami culture. All in all, both entries took good places, fourth and seventh respectively, which is noteworthy, considering the chain of disappointments the voting would bring to NRK over the ensuing years (Arntsen, 2005, p. 147). Brockstedt, who had a prolific career, was indeed the most popular Norwegian singer of the period (Arneberg, 2015). To sum up, in accordance with our first objective we can note that the Sami were represented in this first case study by a popular singer, a leading authority in the field of light music, but distanced from the culture of said ethnic group. This representation was oriented from a friendly and playful, but also stereotypical, perspective. Although the music does not incorporate any ethnic references, there are allusions to ethnicity in the lyrics. The Sami people are linked to a female figure (the girl) connected to nature and magic as well, taking one of the expressions of the Sami language simply as the leitmotif of the song. The scenography and costumes used in the performance reinforce this idea (Figure 1).

However, after the precedent set by the success of ‘*Voi-Voi*’, the Sami theme would no longer be present in any NRK submissions for the following two decades, with the relative exception of the participation of two non-Sami singers born in the Norwegian Lapland: Kirsti Sparboe (Tromsø, 1946), in 1965, 1967, and 1969; and Odd Børre (Harstad, 1939–2023), in 1968. None of them included any reference to Sami culture in their songs. But it is noteworthy to state that late ‘60s saw some advances in the Sami struggle—an ‘ethnic mobilization’ in its own right, as the media of the time put it (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 195)—after a series of industrialisation policies enforced in Lapland, with a strong opposition from the locals, who reacted by founding, in 1968, the political party Norwegian Sami Association (NSR) (Berg, 2008, p. 11). In the same year, a new outstanding cultural celebrity emerged: the Sami singer Nils-Aslak Valkeapää. Finnish-born, in his album ‘*Joikuja*’ (Valkeapää, 1968) sang in the Sami northern dialect, thus going one step further than Jonsson and Brockstedt. Besides, he incorporated *joik* into his compositions, in combination with other sung stanzas (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 194, pp. 196–197). The *joik* had an important symbolic value. Associated with shamanistic rituals (p. 193), was condemned during the ‘Norwegianisation’ period and described as primitive and barbarous, on account of its simple, repetitive, poor structure and its lack of instrumental accompaniment and textual narrative (Paine, 1987, p. 176).

Figure 1. Nora Brockstedt singing 'Voi-Voi' in the 1960 ESC and the cover of her single. Own elaboration based on Eurovision del Siglo XX HD (2018) and Eurovision-Spain (n.d.).

3.2. 'Lapponia' (1977) and the Sami during the 1970s

In the 1970s took place the implementation of government incentives for Sami herders from Norway, Sweden and Finland to abandon their profession with the aim of industrialising their lands (Ahlness & Gauto, 2019, p. 64). In response, in 1971 the Norwegian Sami Council was established, which served to assert claims over their right to land, and in 1975 the Sami people participated in the World Council of Indigenous Peoples (WCIP) (Berg, 2008, p. 11). It was also a time of creative effervescence. Some artistic works, such as John Persen's opera 'Under Kors og Krone' (1976)—which deals with the Kautokeino rebellion, a case of ethnic resistance—became overtly political (Hilder, 2015, pp. 58–59). In the same vein, the following years saw the creation of the first Sami publishing house and the first radio station, as well as their own Educational Council. All these actions allowed them to disseminate their culture, especially their music (Berg, 2008, p. 12; Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 197).

As far as the ESC is concerned, this time the Finnish state television network took over the representation of the Sami on two consecutive occasions. The singer Monica Aspelund (Vaasa, 1946) aspired to represent her country in 1976 with the song 'Joiku', co-wrote with Aarno Raninen (Aspelund, 1976), but failed to be shortlisted at the national qualification stage of the contest. In 1977, she ran again, and this time succeeded in reaching the final, which took place in London, with the song 'Lapponia', also co-authored with Raninen. As can be seen, the titles of both songs relate to Sami culture. The term 'Joiku' of the first one is an inflection of *joik*, the vocal technique imitated by Aspelund in her singing (Gaski, 2008, p. 359). As regards 'Lapponia', it immediately takes us to that region. Nonetheless, as said before, it would be more correct the use of the term 'Sápmi', as this community find 'Lapponia' derogatory, being mainly used by foreigners (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 190).

On a visual level, and specifically costume-wise, whereas in 'Joiku' Aspelund's dress sported the typical colors of the *gákti* (red, blue, and yellow), the performance of 'Lapponia' did not incorporate any striking Sami-related elements other than a silver necklace, a pair of earrings and a bracelet inspired by local craftsmanship. However, the rest of her outfit was interesting because it included a nod to the country that actually submitted the song. Aspelund wore a stripped-back poncho and a slanted skirt, all strictly white decorated with a dark blue stripe parallel to the hem of the poncho. These colours correspond to those of the Finnish flag—a 'banal' way, according to Billig (2014), to conjure up the country. The evocation is further reinforced by other means in the promotional music video, which opens with a close-up of an ancient map of Scandinavia lying on the rack of the piano on which Raninen's hands are playing the accompaniment. Aspelund is standing behind the instrument and looks at the camera while singing, dressed similarly as in 'Joiku'. A scene follows a set in a snow-covered landscape, where the singer appears in several shots wearing a knit cap and a scarf, acting to feel cold. A group of extras is seen drawing the letters YLE (the acronym for the Finnish state TV network) on the snowed ground.

With regard to the message of 'Lapponia', some lines of the lyrics—very similar to those of 'Voi-voi'—stand out, once again relating this land to feminine condition, in this case through a woman voice singing in Finnish. The northern girl who before sang the vernacular greeting, now utters a strange echo: 'Lapland, this is Lapland, from where the pretty northern girl's echo is calling'. The call then turns into a spell: 'The girl is a witch. She creates with the power of fate. She has no company or consolation, that's why she is a witch. She creates with the power of spells' (Aspelund, 1977). As can be seen, Sami culture is again linked with the female roles, and at the same time with magic. The lyrics go as follows: 'A man left for the North, he goes down the road by listening to his instincts. The man falls in love with the witch. He is an earthly human being and that's why the witch must go away. She flies away in the company of the fire of the sky and the echo of the spell' (Aspelund, 1977). Speaking of the onstage performance, lyrics and melody kept in step with the emphatic hand gestures the singer made to convey the casting of the spell. The types of shots—medium shot and close up shot, combined with some long shots—, as well as its position—from the left to the right of the scenery—, its moving—adding also some edition, like transitions or fades to white—and, of course, its number—21 shots—reinforce the composition of these images, adding dynamism.

The topic of the witch is very significant in Sami culture. The witch is linked with the figure of the shaman (Burgos González, 2014, p. 70), someone 'able to communicate with spirits, a mediator between different dimensions' (Kalvig, 2020, p. 4). This issue raises the question of 'ludic ritualization' (widespread in contemporary popular culture), which in this case aestheticises Sami spirituality in a playful way, passing over the fact that a large part of that community actually professes Christianity (pp. 11–12). As in the case with 'Voi-voi' and 'Joiku', the music score does not include any specific Sami elements such as traditional instruments or characteristic melodies; instead, it is a pop song rhythmically accented by clapping and percussion, which give the melody a dynamic feeling that arouses no more than a skin-deep 'thirst for exoticism' in the audience (Hilder, 2015, p. 58). It is worth noting the extremely high note sung in the bridge of the song, a vocal feat that interrupts the flow of the music to conjure up the spell (Vatka, 2021). Regarding its reception, the performance achieved a good tenth place out of eighteen, and the song made its way beyond the Finnish borders, with cover versions being recorded in Dutch, English, German, French, and Swedish, which opened the doors to the international record market for the singer (Kerttula, 2016). As a matter of fact, 'Lapponia' was the only song from the YLE selected for the ESC 50th Anniversary Album, released in 2005 (Rystä & Säilynoja, 2007).

Figure 2. Monica Aspelund singing 'Lapponia' in the 1977 ESC, and a promotional photograph. Own elaboration based on Eurovision Song Contest (2009) and Frantz (2016).

In relation to the first objective, we argue that Sami people are again represented from a privileged voice, as Aspelund is a well-known singer. However, this representation does not come from a Sami voice. In this case, there is no inclusion of words in the Sami language(s), and the term ‘Lapland’, used as the title and as a leitmotif of the song, is an unwelcome concept for the ethnic community. Moreover, the singer’s attire, with its *banal* mention to the Finnish flag, can be interpreted as an allusion to the pre-eminence of national identity over the ethnic claims of this group, which also has its own flag. On this occasion, there is also a reference to the female identity connected to nature and the field of magic, reinforcing the supposed femineity of what is presented as an exotic culture (Figure 2).

Both in ‘Voi-Voi’, written in Norwegian, and in ‘Lapponia’, in Finnish, there is a striking absence of any reference to the Sami languages, except for the greeting expression in the former. Belonging to the Uralic family of languages, there are in fact ten officially recognised Sami languages (Hilder, 2015, p. 46). Northern Sami, with some 30,000 speakers, is the dominant one, given that the assimilation policies enforced since the mid-19th century jeopardised other varieties, such as Inari, Kildin and Skolt (p. 46). In this point, the relationship between the Sami people and the country they live in, becomes more clearly evident, marked by the assimilation policies (like ‘Norwegianisation’ in the case of Norway). As Hilder follows, ‘[t]oday, in fact, only about fifty percent of self-identifying Sámi can speak a Sámi language’ (p. 46). For this reason, more and more artists are becoming committed to its promotion, with the singer and actor Antte Ailu Gaup, from Kautokeino, as a paradigmatic case, combining traditional and rock music (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 199).

3.3. ‘Sámiid Ædnan’ (1980) and the Sami during the 1980s

In the late 1970s, this people found itself at a difficult juncture, on account of the intensification of the industrialisation policies in its lands (Hilder, 2015, pp. 59–60; Svensson, 1987, p. 138). As early as in 1978, the artist Trygve Lund Guttormsen called for action during the Alta Controversy, a conflict brought about by the government project to build a hydroelectric power station in the Alta river, in the Norwegian county of Troms og Finnmark (Paine, 1985, 1987, p. 96; Svensson, 1987, p. 140). The construction would wash away the Sami town of Masi and disrupt reindeer migration and wild salmon fishing. The affected community held numerous protests, which lasted from summer to early autumn 1979 (Hilder, 2015, p. 39). As Svein T. Andersen & Alte Midttun explain, in these ‘civil disobedience actions, [...] local inhabitants and Norwegian environmental groups blocked the construction of a road up to the site for the planned power station’ (1985, p. 319). Although ‘police were called in and arrests made’, they did not ‘succeed [...] in clearing the way’ (p. 319).

It is relevant that music was very much present throughout the protests, to such an extent that Thomas Hilder claims the *joik* anthem ‘Sámi Eatnan Duoddarat’ to have become the soundtrack of the revolution (2015, p. 59). The actions continued to the point that, in October 8, 1979, ‘a group of Sámi activists pitched a tent [called *lavvu* in Sami language] in front of the Norwegian Parliament in Oslo and went on a week-long hunger strike. During the protest, the activists would sing *Sámi Eatnan Duoddarat*, thus linking *joik* to [...] resistance’ (p. 39). The action was endorsed by the political organisation SAG, and, against all odds, the sympathies of the Oslo citizens were with them (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 200). Such was the popular support that the following year (1980), when the Sami Rights Committee was created, Mattis Hætta (Masi, 1959–2022) became the first Sami singer to perform in the ESC and, what is more, to bring their plight to light. After winning the national song contest jointly with the famous pop-rock singer Sverre Kjelsberg (Tromsø, 1946–2016) (p. 201), the couple represented the NRK in The Hague, Netherlands (Motschenbacher, 2016, p. 31). Both came from the region threatened by the project.

In that edition, a novelty was introduced: for the first time, each participating country was presented not by local hosts but by public national personalities, who expressly travelled to the host city to say a few words of introduction (O’Connor, 2007, p. 80). On that occasion, the Norwegian state TV chose the Labour Party member and Minister of Culture, aside from a well-known singer, Åse Kleveland, who had represented her country in the 1966 edition as well, winning the bronze medal (Motschenbacher, 2016, p. 20). Her words went as follows:

In recent years, the world's indigenous peoples have increasingly asserted the right to retain their culture, their language and, above all, the right to land they have inhabited since immemorial time. This applies to a large extent to the Norwegian Sami. This is what Norway's entry is about here tonight. 'Sámiid Ædnan' means the country of the Sami. (EBU, 1980, 49'13").

Anyway, this statement set a frame for the subsequent reception of the song by an international audience,² tying its message to a very specific context and so directing its interpretation. The power station would involve the creation of a reservoir and the washing away of the town of Masi. In these circumstances, the song 'Sámiid Ædnan', composed by Kjelsberg and the songwriter Ragnar Olsen, served as an indictment of the situation, expressed through both music and lyrics (Hilder, 2015, p. 59). Although its style is primarily pop-rock, halfway through the song the *joik* technique makes its appearance, a Sami national emblem. As Robert Paine explains, 'by the 1970s, the *joik* had been 'rediscovered', and not just by ethnomusicologists but by young Sami', who would then start incorporating it into the mainstream popular music of the time (1987, p. 176). The records released were a great success, even reaching 'the top of the charts in Norway' (p. 176). In this context, with 'Sámiid Ædnan' the experienced singer Sverre Kjelsberg moved 'the conflict surrounding the Alta project into a much broader arena of public discourse' (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 201). The lyrics of 'Sámiid Ædnan' go as follows:

A simple tune, just two words: *Sámiid Ædnan*, Sami Land. It came with the wind from the north, from the north, *Sámiid Ædnan*. Is it possible to achieve anything peacefully? *Sámiid Ædnan*, Sami Land. It grew from a breeze to a storm, from a breeze to a storm, *Sámiid Ædnan*. In front of the Parliament where they sat—*Sámiid Ædnan*, Sami Land—the *joik* is heard day and night, *Sámiid Ædnan*. (Kjelsberg & Hætta, 1980)

All this section is sung solo by Kjelsberg. His performance 'begins *sotto voce*, and gradually builds in intensity' (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 201), until a sudden silence gives way to Hætta's *joik*. He also starts in a near-whisper, which keeps growing in intensity along with the accompaniment in 'a long, gradual crescendo' (p. 201). He chose 'a traditional *joik* from his region that made exclusive use of the vocables "lo" and "la", whose simplicity should mean a chance to reach a mainstream audience (p. 201). Come the final bars, Kjelsberg rejoins; both voices intersect, showing an 'amazing zeal' (p. 201) that suits the radicality of the statement sung by Kjelsberg: '*Joik* is more powerful than weapons... as it has no beginning nor end'—a new allusion to the riots, as well as to the peculiarity of this singing (p. 201). Not bound by any precise starting or ending points, the temporality of the *joik* is subject to parameters unaware of chronological time, being able to be construed even as a counter-narrative or even an alternative one (Ahlness & Gauto, 2019, p. 65). After his statement, Kjelsberg goes quiet, and it is Hætta who closes the song.

In a visual level, while Kjelsberg wore a then-fashionable white suit, the ethnic claim is reinforced by the traditional *gákti* from Hætta, making his message more visible (Aronson, 2017, p. 37; Hilder, 2015, p. 39). Nonetheless, this creates an intriguing dichotomy. On the one hand, it establishes a link—a conciliatory link—between tradition and modernity; and on the other hand this fact can be interpreted as the only way the indigenous can be staged in the international arena: only by means of the previous presentation of the man in the normative 'occidental' suit. Regarding other elements of its *mise-en-scène*, lighting is also a very important part of this performance because the part of Kjelsberg looks very luminous, while the one from Hætta starts after the switching off of lights and only little by little it will increase its luminance. Although in 'Voi-Voi' a simple decorate can be found in the background, in 'Sámiid Ædnan' there is no other relevant *mise-en-scène* element, like in 'Lapponia'. The number of shots is similar to the latter—19—, with plenty of fades in-between, a lot of movements too, and it is interesting that most of the close up are starred by Kjelsberg. More critics can be found, in this case, in the title of 'Sámiid Ædnan' (which announces the content and is repeated several times in the piece), in Sami language (but only Northern Sami), whereas the rest of the lyrics are in Norwegian. Second, Kjelsberg seems to hold the lead role in the performance, while Hætta, with his *joik*, does not to express any textual meaning. The fact that it is Kjelsberg who speaks out on behalf of the Sami (Hilder, 2015, p. 58) puts him in a privileged position, that of an interpreter or mediator, instead of giving the floor to Hætta's words (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 202).

Regarding the reception of the song, its originality did not find favour with the ESC juries. It achieved only third-to-last place (Hilder, 2017, p. 30), supported by the votes of just three countries out of eighteen: Germany, the Netherlands, and France. Some of the reasons behind this failure must lie in the political stance of the song, as well as in its style, a far cry from the commercial pop prevailing at the time (Björnberg & Bossius, 2017, p. 6). However, despite the low score, 'Sámiid Ædnan' would eventually become a success in the Scandinavian countries (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 202), further boosted by the great social significance the *joik* had achieved by then (Hilder, 2015, p. 39). Connecting with our first objective, it can be found that for the first time the Sami people are represented by themselves, although only one of the members of the duo comes from this ethnic group, and most of the song is not written in the Sami language. As has been analysed, the very structure of the composition, the singers' interpretation and their costumes reinforce the differential fact of belonging to this people, thus intoning a message radically different from the one that has been launched in the two previous case studies. Moreover, it is an explicitly politicised message, which positions this ethnic group as a first-rate interlocutor, transcending the sphere of entertainment or fantasy, to which such proposals are usually addressed. In fact, 'Sámiid Ædnan' became a song inevitable linked to the revolution of that time as well as an unusual message from the local to the global witnessed by millions of viewers. This song coexisted with the resistance strategies abovementioned, which finally led to the government project being reassessed (Jones-Bamman, 2001, p. 200). The power station would have a much lower impact on the county, with no populated areas being washed away (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Sami nonviolent resistance during the Alta Controversy demonstrations (left), and Mattis Hætta and Sverre Kjelsberg gesture next to a *lavvu* in front of the Nederlands Congresgebouw (host venue to the The Hague 1980 ESC), in allusion to the Oslo protests (right). Own elaboration based on Renå (2019) and Johansen (2016).

As we can infer, 'Sámiid Ædnan', the soundtrack of this process, would get a positive influence in the Sami culture. In fact, it would be the best-known *joik* worldwide (Hansen, 2015, p. 181) and one of the first learnt by Sami children at school (Hilder, 2017, p. 30). Those facts coincide with the context (the 1980s) when many politics made the ethnic group gain greater recognition. In 1986 the Sami flag and anthem were made official (Hilder, 2015, p. 38), and in 1989 Sami parliaments in Norway, Sweden and Finland were created (Ren & Thisted, 2021, p. 303). Finally, in 1990, took place the ratification of the ILO Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention (No. 169) (Hilder, 2017, p. 30). This politics coincide too with the raise of musical events like the Sami Easter Festival or the Sami Grand Prix (pp. 30–31), and the emergence of artists like the band Almetjh Tjööngkeme and the singer Mari Boine (Jones-Bamman, 2001, pp. 203–206).

4. Conclusions

From the analysis conducted, a number of observations can be made as to the representation of the Sami people in the ESC. With regard to the objectives of this investigation, the three case studies analysed present the following key features:

- a. Concerning the contents, although all the songs allude to the Sami culture, only one of them—‘Sámiid Ædnan’—goes significantly deeper. ‘Voi-Voi’ and ‘Lapponia’ tell the story of a woman linked to Sami culture in an amusing way, without referring concrete aspects of this culture. This way, these messages can be applied to other contexts, expanding its interpretations. Nonetheless, the latter is very explicit: the entry focuses on a political message, framed in a serious performance. Moreover, unlike the ‘Sámiid Ædnan’, the two first songs are performed and written by non-Sami artists, what creates a distance between the message and the sender of that message.
- b. As regards costumes, references were made to local ethnic garments in both ‘Voi-voi’ and ‘Sámiid Ædnan’. Still, only in the latter an authentic Sami *gákti* was worn, since the former featured just an adapted version. As to Monica Aspelund, the dress she wore in ‘Lapponia’ contained an interesting nod to her own culture, although restricted to the national flag. The *mise-en-scène* of these proposals was limited to a simple backdrop in 1960, to a TV production in tune with the rhythms of the song in 1977, and to the lighting game in 1980. As at this phase the contest was not yet so spectacular on a scenic level, the visual identity was mainly reflected in the costumes.
- c. As far as the reception is concerned, the first two entries scored quite well in the voting, while the third one remained near the bottom of the scoreboard; but only ‘Sámiid Ædnan’, which was linked to the Sami revolution, would be a huge commercial success in the Scandinavian countries, becoming one of the best-known *joik* in history. This aspect raises a question: Who is really the addressee of the song submitted to the festival—the global audience, or the community about which the song is sung and, where appropriate, to which the performers belong? It is clear, therefore, that the first two are aimed at the general public while the latter is not necessarily so. This can explain the results obtained in the show.
- d. In relation to the debate on resistance and aesthetisation, the first two cases did not tackle effective resistance at all, although they shed light—albeit superficial—on the Sami people by taking advantage of the incomparable international stage provided by the event. As to the third case, the ESC put forward, by placing a Sami indigenous body in the centre, what can be interpreted as a true narrative of resistance. Nonetheless, the fact that he did not take the opportunity to express himself verbally (which his non-Sami fellow performer did instead) is open to criticism.

All in all, these issues revolve around a very delicate matter within the Scandinavian countries. In 1987, Tom G. Svensson affirmed that ‘on the international stage, the Scandinavians have always advocated minority rights, [...] highly prioritizing human rights issues. But these principles are not compatible with internal political realities’ (1987, p. 146). Hilder resumed the question arguing that these countries, ‘guardians of “Western” democratic principles’ (2017, p. 27) when it comes to gender, sexuality and environmental issues—what makes them ‘havens of social justice and peace’ (p. 23)—at the same time have disregarded ethnic claims (p. 28) and adopted ‘neoliberal economy policies [...] [and] a strict approach to immigration [...], and seen a resurgence of right-wing nationalist sentiment’ (p. 24). In sum, there is no doubt that the Alta Controversy was a turning point in the way minorities would participate in politics, with aesthetics being very much present throughout the whole process.

Finally, it is remarkable to state that, after participating in 1980, no one Sami singer would return to the competition until very recently—a fact that underlines the renewed interest in the issue. As said before, the proposal of Roger Pontare will be an outstanding exception in 2000, with a song including the *joik* and entitled ‘When Spirits are Calling My Name’. After some intents in pre-selections (among others, see Jon Henrik Fjällgren in Melodifestivalen in 2015, 2017, 2019 and 2023) and semifinals (Agnete, representing the NRK in 2016), in 2019 Fred Buljo, a *joik* Sami singer, will represent Norway in the ESC as a member of the band KEiiNO. This time the song, entitled ‘Spirit in the Sky’, will achieve a great success within the competition, even being the most voted by the public (Kalvig, 2020, p. 8; Ren & Thisted 2021, p. 302). Undoubtedly, an interesting contrast with Hætta & Kjelsberg’s song can be found in this respect. Hence, the approach proposed in this article can provide a solid context to understand the recent Sami audiovisual narratives in the show, when a resurgence of this question starts to be taking place.

About the author

José Luis Panea is a Professor in the Department of Aesthetics and History of Philosophy at University of Seville, Spain. He pioneered the research in Spain about the aesthetics and politics of the Eurovision Song Contest, with numerous articles published and participations in international conferences, always in close cooperation with the media.

Notes

1. In fact, there are no restrictions regarding this issue. As any other people or community, the Sami are eligible to represent any other country, although this has never happened to date. Some other traditional cultures do have seen their traditions (e.g. the yodel singing technique from Tirol, or Spanish rumba) borrowed by other countries (Romania in 2017 and Finland in 1989, respectively) (Motschenbacher, 2016, pp. 153–188).
2. Here is valuable to add also how other broadcasters from the show translated that speech. The one from Miguel de los Santos' Spanish broadcaster RTVE, available also for this research since our research comes from a Spanish institution, reads: 'Good evening. The Norwegian contribution to this contest is inspired by the conflict between the northern autochthonous peoples with the more advanced ones over the preservation of their musical traditions, and to prevent the peace of their lands from being invaded by overdevelopment and technification' (EBU, 1980, 49'13").

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References

- Ahness, E. A., & Gauto, M. G. (2019). Decolonizar los espacios grises: el arte y la narración como activismo político de los samis. *Ecología Política*, 57, 62–67. <https://www.ecologiapolitica.info/decolonizar-los-espacios-grise-s-el-arte-y-la-narracion-como-activismo-politico-de-los-samis/>
- Alfred, G. T. (1999). *Peace, power, righteousness: An Indigenous manifesto*. Oxford University Press.
- Andersen, S. T., & Midttun, A. (1985). Conflict and local mobilization: The Alta hydropower project. *Acta Sociologica*, 28(4), 317–335. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000169938502800402>
- Arneberg, H. (2015, November 5). Nora Brockstedt er død. *Aftenposten*. <https://www.aftenposten.no/kultur/i/8X5r/nora-brockstedt-er-doed>
- Arntsen, H. (2005). Staging the nation? Nation, myth and cultural stereotypes in the International Eurovision Song Contest Finals in Estonia, Latvia and Norway. In R. Baerung (Ed.), *Baltic media world* (pp. 145–157). Flera Printing-House.
- Aronson, B. (2017). The white savior industrial complex: A cultural studies analysis of a teacher educator, savior film, and future teachers. *Journal of Critical Thought and Praxis*, 6(3), 36–54. <https://doi.org/10.31274/jctp-180810-83>

- Aspelund, M. (1976). Joiku [Song]. On *Joiku* [Single]. RCA Victor.
- Aspelund, M. (1977). Lapponia [Song]. On *Lapponia* [Album]. RCA Victor.
- Baker, C. (2017). The 'gay Olympics'? The Eurovision Song Contest and the politics of LGBT/European belonging. *European Journal of International Relations*, 23(1), 97–121. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354066116633278>
- Benjamin, W. (2015). La obra de arte en la época de su reproductibilidad técnica. In T. Vera Barros (Ed.), *Estética de la imagen: fotografía, cine y pintura* (pp. 25–81). La Marca Editora.
- Berg, B. A. (2008). Remapping Sápmi: Sámi cooperation and connectivity across national borders. *Báiki International Sami Journal*, 29, 10–13. <http://www.saamibaiki.org/content/Baiki/contents21-30.html>
- Bhabha, H. K. (2003). El entre-medio de la cultura. In S. Hall & P. du Gay (Eds.), *Cuestiones de identidad cultural* (pp. 94–106). Amorrortu.
- Billig, M. (2014). *Nacionalismo banal*. Capitán Swing.
- Björnberg, A., & Bossius, T. (2017). The small country that grew big in popular music. In A. Björnberg & T. Bossius (Eds.), *Made in Sweden. Studies in popular music* (pp. 1–9). Routledge.
- Bolin, G. (2010). Media events, eurovision and societal centers. In N. Couldry, A. Hepp, & F. Krotz (Eds.), *Media events in a Global Age* (pp. 124–138). Routledge.
- Brockstedt, N. (1960). Voi-voi [Song]. On *Voi-voi* [Single]. Karusell.
- Brockstedt, N. (1961). Sommer i Palma [Song]. On *Sommer i Palma* [Single]. Karusell.
- Burgos González, T. (2014). Noaidi: El Chamán Sámi y su función de mago. *Ilú. Revista de Ciencias de las Religiones*, 19, 65–91. https://doi.org/10.5209/rev_ILUR.2014.v19.46612
- Collins, J. L., & Barker, L. (2019). Indigenous representation at the Eurovision Song Contest: A quintessentially Australian identity. In C. Hay & J. Carniel (Eds.), *Eurovision and Australia interdisciplinary perspectives from down under* (pp. 57–74). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Dyck, N. (Ed.). (1985). *Indigenous peoples and the nation state: Fourth world politics in Canada, Australia and Norway*. St John's, Memorial University of Newfoundland.
- EBU (Director). (1980). *Eurovision Song Contest* [TV show]. NOS.
- Fornäs, J. (2017). Euro-visions: East European narratives in televised popular music. In J. Fornäs (Ed.), *Europe faces Europe. Narratives from its eastern half* (pp. 179–235). Intellect, The University of Chicago Press.
- Fricke, K. (2015). Eurovision and the "New" Europe. In K. Mitscha & K. Unterberger (Eds.), *Texte 14. Public service media in Europe. Eurovision Song Contest: More than music?* (pp. 8–15). Österreichischer Rundfunk.
- García Varas, A. (2011). Lógica(s) de la imagen. In A. García Varas (Ed.), *Filosofía de la imagen* (pp. 15–46). Ediciones Universidad de Salamanca.
- Gaski, H. (2008). Yoik-Sami music in a global world. In H. Minde (Ed.), *Indigenous peoples: Self-determination knowledge indigeneity* (pp. 347–361). Eburon Academic Publishers.
- Gibbs, J. (2002). *Mise-En-Scène: Film style and interpretation*. Wallflower Press.
- Giménez, G. (2006). El debate contemporáneo en torno al concepto de etnicidad. *Cultura y Representaciones Sociales*, 1(1), 129–144. <https://www.culturayrs.unam.mx/index.php/CRS/article/view/495>
- Gómez-Pérez, F. J., & Pérez-Rufí, J. P. (2022). Análisis de la realización de espectáculos televisivos en directo: Italia en Eurovisión 2021. *Index Comunicacion*, 12(1), 235–259. <https://doi.org/10.33732/ixc/12/01Analisis>
- Gross, A. (2015). The politics of LGBT rights in Israel and beyond: Nationality, normativity, and queer politics. *Columbia Human Rights Law Review*, 46(2), 81–152. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3065040
- Hansen, K. V. (2015). *Being Sami: An ethnography of identity through the lens of the Riddu Riddu Festival* [PhD thesis, Australian National University]. <http://hdl.handle.net/1885/108736>
- Hilder, T. (2015). Performing Sápmi. In T. Hilder (Ed.), *Sami musical performance and the politics of indigeneity in Northern Europe* (pp. 35–70). Rowman & Littlefield.
- Hilder, T. (2017). Nordic sexual exceptionalism and Indigenous rights: Sámi alternative visions of Europe at the Eurovision Song Contest. In M. Färnkranz & U. Hemetek (Eds.), *Performing sexual identities. Nationalities on the eurovision stage* (pp. 23–43). Institut für Volksmusikforschung und Ethnomusikologie.
- Hindrichs, T. (2007). Chasing the magic formula for success: Ralph Siegel and the Grand Prix Eurovision de la Chanson. In I. Raykoff & R. Deam Tobin (Eds.), *A song for Europe. Popular music and politics in the Eurovision Song Contest* (pp. 49–60). Ashgate.
- Hobsbawm, E., & Ranger, T. (Eds.). (2000). *The invention of tradition*. Cambridge University Press.
- Jarque, V. (2002). *Experiencia histórica y arte contemporáneo. Ensayos de Estética y modelos de crítica*. Ediciones Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha.
- Jiménez, J. (2020). ¿En qué imagen vivimos?. In F. Infante-del-Rosal, A. Molina Flores, & V. Moura (Eds.), *Estética, arte y política* (pp. 11–29). Publicacions Universitat de València.
- Jones-Bamman, R. (2001). From 'I'm a Lapp' to 'I am Saami': Popular music and changing images of Indigenous ethnicity in Scandinavia. *Journal of Intercultural Studies*, 22(2), 189–210. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07256860120069602>
- Kalvig, A. (2020). Nature and magic as representation of "The Sami" – Sami shamanistic material in popular culture. *Religions*, 11(9), 453. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel11090453>
- Kerttula, S. (2016, July 9). Hyvä sisaruussuhde on suuri aarre. *Iltasanomat*. <https://www.is.fi/perhe/art-2000001214418.html>
- Kjelsberg, S., & Hætta, M. (1980). Sámiid Ædnan [Song]. On *Sámiid Ædnan* [Single]. Plateselskapet Mai/Polydor.

- Lampropoulos, A. (2013). Lausanne-Zagreb via Berlin, or heading for an unforeseen Europeanness. *Journal of European Popular Culture*, 4(2), 139–154. https://doi.org/10.1386/jepc.4.2.139_1
- Lee, S. (2016). Wes Anderson's ambivalent film style: The relation between mise-en-scène and emotion. *New Review of Film and Television Studies*, 14(4), 409–439. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17400309.2016.1172858>
- Martin, A. (2014). *Mise-En-Scène and film style: From classical hollywood to new media art*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Martínez Carazo, P. (2006). El método de estudio de caso: estrategia metodológica de la investigación científica. *Pensamiento and Gestión*, 20, 165–193. <https://rciencifcas.uninorte.edu.co/index.php/pensamiento/article/view/3576>
- Martínez-Collado, A. (2008). Narraciones/visibilizaciones de la diferencia en la cultura de la interfaz. In A. Notario-Ruiz (Ed.), *Estética: perspectivas contemporáneas* (pp. 89–128). Ediciones Universidad de Salamanca.
- Motschenbacher, H. (2016). *Language, normativity and Europeanism. Discursive evidence from the Eurovision Song Contest*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- O'Connor, J. K. (2007). *The Eurovision Song Contest. The official history*. Carlton Books.
- Oksanen, A.-A. (2020). The rise of Indigenous (pluri-)nationalism: The case of the Sámi people. *Sociology*, 54(6), 1141–1158. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038038520943105>
- Oliver, S. (Director) (2011). *The secret history of Eurovision* [Documentary]. Brook Lapping Productions and Electric Pictures.
- Paine, R. (1985). Ethnodrama and the 'Fourth World': The Saami Action Group in Norway, 1979–1981. In N. Dyck (Ed.), *Indigenous peoples and the nation state: Fourth world politics in Canada, Australia and Norway* (pp. 190–235). St John's, Memorial University of Newfoundland.
- Paine, R. (1987). Trails of Saami self-consciousness. *Anthropologica*, 29(2), 169–188. <https://doi.org/10.2307/25605229>
- Pajala, M. (2011). Making television historical: Cultural memory of the Eurovision Song Contest in the Finnish media. 1961–2005. *Media History*, 17(4), 405–418. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13688804.2011.602859>
- Pajala, M. (2013). Europe, with feeling. The Eurovision Song Contest as Entertainment. In K. Fricker & M. Gluhovic (Eds.), *Performing the 'New' Europe: Identities, feelings and politics in the Eurovision Song Contest* (pp. 77–93). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Pajala, M. (2022). The Eurovision Song Contest and European Television History: Continuity, adaptation, experimentation. In A. Dubin, A. Obregón García, & D. Vuletic (Eds.), *The Eurovision Song Contest as a cultural phenomenon. From concert halls to the halls of Academia* (pp. 188–200). Routledge.
- Panea, J. L. (2020). Las escenografías del Festival de Eurovisión: Estética, tecnología e identidad cultural al albor de la reconstrucción europea (1956-1993). *Ámbitos. Revista de estudios de Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades*, 44 23–40. <http://hdl.handle.net/10396/21179>
- Panea, J. L. (2022). Domesticity, mass media and moving-image aesthetics: The visual identity of the Eurovision Song Contest as a hospitable platform. In A. Dubin, A. Obregón García, & D. Vuletic (Eds.), *The Eurovision Song Contest as a cultural phenomenon. From concert halls to the halls of Academia* (pp. 219–236). Routledge.
- Pavis, P. (2013). *Contemporary Mise en Scène. Staging theatre today*. Routledge.
- Pérez-Rufí, J. P., & Valverde-Maestre, Á. M. (2020). The spatial-temporal fragmentation of live television video clips: Analysis of the television production of the Eurovision Song Contest. *Communication and Society*, 33(2), 17–31. <https://doi.org/10.15581/003.33.2.17-31>
- Petersen, M. K., & Ren, C. (2015). "Much more than a song contest": Exploring Eurovision 2014 as Potlatch. *Valuation Studies*, 3(2), 97–118. <https://doi.org/10.3384/V5.2001-5992.153297>
- Ren, C., & Thisted, K. (2021). Branding Nordic indigeneities. *Journal of Place Management and Development*, 14(3), 301–314. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPMD-01-2020-0007>
- Ríos Hernández, I. N., & Pinto Arboleda, N. C. (2019). Análisis de narrativa transmedial y documental web no ficcional: estudio de caso miPáramo. *Revista Nexus Comunicación*, 36, 31–51. <https://doi.org/10.25100/nc.v0i26.9266>
- Ruiz de Samaniego, A. (2007). Una estética de la representación posmoderna. *Azafea. Revista de Filosofía*, 9, 61–82. <https://revistas.usal.es/dos/index.php/0213-3563/article/view/641/815>
- Rystä, P., & Säilynoja, J. (2007, January 26). Monica Aspelund: Lapponia. *YLE*. <https://yle.fi/aihe/artikkeli/2007/01/26/monica-aspelund-lapponia>
- Sánchez Fernández, J. M. (2019). *La imagen de nuestro presente*. Dykinson.
- Sánchez Meca, D. (2005). Heidegger, la esencia de la técnica y el destino de Occidente. In M. C. Paredes Martín (Ed.), *Naturaleza y libertad. La filosofía ante los problemas del presente* (pp. 33–46). Sociedad castellano-leonesa de Filosofía.
- Singleton, B., Ekholm, K., Hocking, S., Rusen, M., Franck, J., Sieg, K., Jackson, P., Devine, P., & Jordan, P. (2013). "The song contest is a battlefield": Panel discussion with Eurovision Song Contest broadcasters, 18 February 2011. In K. Fricker & M. Gluhovic (Eds.), *Performing the 'New' Europe: Identities, feelings and politics in the Eurovision Song Contest* (pp. 94–107). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Singleton, B., Fricker, K., & Moreo, E. (2007). Performing the queer network. Fans and families at the Eurovision Song Contest. *SQS: Suomen Queer-Tutkimuskeskus Seuran Lehti*, 2(2), 12–31. <https://journal.fi/sqs/article/view/53665>
- Stolcke, V. (2011). ¿Es el sexo para el género lo que la raza para la etnicidad... y la naturaleza para la sociedad?. In F. Cruces Villalobos & B. Pérez Galán (Eds.), *Textos de Antropología Contemporánea* (pp. 315–348). UNED.
- Svensson, T. G. (1987). Industrial developments and the Sami: Ethnopolitical response to ecological crisis in the North. *Anthropologica*, 29(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.2307/25605227>
- Valkeapää, N.-A. (1968). Joikuja [Album]. Otavan Kirjallinen Äänilevy.

- Vatka, M. (2021, July 16). Lapponia-laulaja Monica Aspelund, 75, lataa nyt suorat sanat nykyviisuista: "Sirkus on erikseen". *Italehti*. <https://www.iltalehti.fi/viihdeuutiset/a/9b582423-3e9e-4a13-acbb-bb229124730a>
- Vuletic, D. (2018). *Postwar Europe and the Eurovision Song Contest*. Bloomsbury.
- Waysdorf, A. S. (2020). "This is our night": Eurovision again and liveness through archives. In P. D. Keidl & L. Melamed (Eds.), *Pandemic media: Preliminary notes towards an inventory* (pp. 295–302). Meson Press.
- Yair, G. (2019). Douze point: Eurovisions and Euro-Divisions in the Eurovision Song Contest. Review of two decades of research. *European Journal of Cultural Studies*, 22(5-6), 1013–1029. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1367549418776562>

Image credits

- Eurovision del Siglo XX HD. (2018, September 1). *ESC 1960 – Noruega. Voi-Voi* [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LnGVJrsu9loandab_channel=EurovisiondelSigloXHHHD
- Eurovision Song Contest. (2009, January 8). *Monica Aspelund sings "Lapponia"* [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=n8AcC4fuHIMandab_channel=EurovisionSongContest
- Eurovision-Spain. (n.d.). *Nora Brockstedt*. <https://eurovision-spain.com/participante/nora-brockstedt-1960/>
- Frantz, E. (2016, February 13). *Lapponia! En snödrottning i London*. Svenska YLE. <https://svenska.yle.fi/a/7-1037078>
- Johansen, T. U. (2016, June 20). *Større kraft enn krutt*. VG Norway. <https://www.vg.no/nyheter/meninger/i/kkoLB/stoerre-kraft-enn-krutt>
- Renå, A. S. (2019, October 15). *Synnøve sultestreiket mot kraftutbygging i 1979. Dette sier Alta-demonstrantene 40 år etter*. Frifagbevegelse. <https://frifagbevegelse.no/nyheter/synnove-sultestreiket-mot-kraftutbygging-i-1979-dette-sier-altademonstrantene-40-ar-etter-6.469.650232.42e7611329>